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Analysis of a quasi-periodic locally resonant mechanical metastructure for piezoelectric energy harvesting applications

M.Sc. IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING - COURSE OF "SMART STRUCTURES AND DEVICES"

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Aim of the work

The purpose of the work conducted by Xia *et al.* [1] was to investigate the dynamic behaviour of a quasi-periodic resonant metastructures, demonstrating that, in addition to the conventional locally resonant ones defined by the resonators natural frequency, the quasi-periodic arrangement of an array of resonators along a free-clamped beam introduces additional non-trivial frequency bandgaps (and related edge states). In this study, computational methods are used to explore the occurrence of these gaps and the related edge states. A further step has been taken by studying the energy harvesting properties of such a structure, taking advantage of the peculiar properties of piezoelectric patches combined with several resistive loads. With reference to what discussed by Sugino *et al.* [2], the total power output as well as the dynamic behaviour of the electro-mechanical metastructure is analyzed, paying special attention to the effects of quasi-periodic distribution of the resonators set.

Figure 1: Projection operation underlying the QP resonators distribution along the beam span as described by Xia *et al.* [1].

Table 1: Problem data as described by Xia *et al.* [1].

Feature	Symbol	Unit	Value
Circle center spacing	a	mm	5
Circle radius	R	mm	1.5
Number of resonator locations	S	–	30
Projection angle	θ	rad	$[1, \dots, S] / S$
Beam length	L	mm	1524
Beam width	b	mm	25.2
Beam thickness	h	mm	0.8
Beam density	ρ	kg/m^3	2700
Elastic modulus	E	GPa	69
Resonators tuning frequency	f_T	Hz	90
Resonators / beam mass ratio	μ	–	1.26

1. Problem description and theoretical background

As briefly described in the introduction, the subject of the study is a cantilever beam under transverse motion equipped with quasi-periodically distributed resonators. With reference to Figure 1, this quasi-periodic (QP) distribution is achieved through a projection operation: the periodic spacing between the centers of a set of equally spaced circumferences is altered by the addition of a function of an increasing angle. As a result, the location of the resonator s is given by:

$$x_s = sa + R \sin(2\pi \cdot s\theta) \quad (1)$$

Here, a is the spacing between two subsequent circumferences centers, R is the circumference radius and the parameter θ defines the particular QP distribution. To be noted that, being 2π the periodicity of the sin function, by selecting a rational $\theta = p/q$ it is possible to resemble to a distribution with a spatial period of qa . This feature was exploited by Xia *et al.* [1] in order to set up different configurations with the last resonator positioned at the free end of the aluminum beam. Experiment parameters are displayed within Table 1. To be noted that all resonators are assumed to be equal in terms of equivalent mass and stiffness.

Therefore, referring to the beam traversal displacement as $w(x, t)$ and to the relative displacement between the s -th resonator and $w(x_s, t)$ as $u_s(t)$, the set of equations describing the undamped system is:

$$\begin{cases} EJ \frac{\partial^4 w(x, t)}{\partial x^4} + m \frac{\partial^2 w(x, t)}{\partial t^2} = \sum_{s=1}^S k_T u_s(t) \delta(x - x_s) \\ \ddot{u}_s + \omega_T^2 u_s = - \frac{\partial^2 w(x, t)}{\partial t^2} \Big|_{x_s} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where J is the second moment of area of the beam cross section, $m = \rho A$ is the linear mass density of the beam, δ is the Dirac delta function, k_T and ω_T are the resonator's stiffness and target angular frequency respectively. Before investigating the resonator's effect on the beam response to a base motion and their energy harvesting capability after placing piezoelectric patches, it is necessary to

briefly introduce the concept of bulk spectrum [3] and its relation to the natural frequencies of the beam.

1.1. Bulk and finite beam spectrum as a function of θ

It is possible to define the so-called *bulk spectrum* as the set of the natural frequencies of an infinite beam with the same properties of the one object of the study. In other words, materials and geometric properties of the infinite beam are unchanged, while the resonators distribution has a periodicity of L so as the structure, in practice, resembles to a ring of perimeter L .

In order to evaluate the spectrum of both beams as a function of θ it is necessary to reformulate the set of equations governing the system (2) as an eigenvalue problem [3]. It is then possible to apply modal decomposition approach to both beam models by a proper selection of the modal shapes adopted.

For what concerning the cantilever beam, the characteristic equation associated to the boundary conditions of the problem is:

$$1 + \cos(\gamma L) \cosh(\gamma L) \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the mode shape associated to the n -th solution of the characteristic equation is:

$$\phi_n(x) = \cosh(\gamma_n x) - \cos(\gamma_n x) - A_n \left(\sinh(\gamma_n x) - \sin(\gamma_n x) \right) \quad (4)$$

where

$$A_n = \frac{\cos(\gamma_n L) + \cosh(\gamma_n L)}{\sin(\gamma_n L) + \sinh(\gamma_n L)}$$

However, this form suffers from numerical instability for high n when x approaches the end of the beam, since in that case $A_n \approx 1$ and therefore $\phi_n(x) \approx \cosh(\gamma_n x) - \sinh(\gamma_n x)$ i.e. a small number is computed as the difference between two big numbers. Consequently, with reference to [4], it is possible to define the parameter ν as:

$$\nu = A_n - 1 = \frac{\cos(\gamma_n L) + \cosh(\gamma_n L) - \sin(\gamma_n L) - \sinh(\gamma_n L)}{\sin(\gamma_n L) + \sinh(\gamma_n L)} = \frac{e^{-\gamma_n L} + \cos(\gamma_n L) - \sin(\gamma_n L)}{\sin(\gamma_n L) + \sinh(\gamma_n L)}$$

which, substituted back into (4), gives:

$$\phi_n(x) = \cosh(\gamma_n x) - \cos(\gamma_n x) - (1 + \nu) \left(\sinh(\gamma_n x) - \sin(\gamma_n x) \right) = e^{-\gamma_n x} - \cos(\gamma_n x) + (1 + \nu) \sin(\gamma_n x) - \nu \sinh(\gamma_n x) \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) still describes the exact solution. It is possible to further refine its behaviour when dealing with high order modes by considering the following approximation:

$$\nu \sinh(\gamma_n x) = \frac{e^{-\gamma_n L} + \cos(\gamma_n L) - \sin(\gamma_n L)}{\underbrace{\sin(\gamma_n L) + \sinh(\gamma_n L)}_{\mathcal{O}(\sinh(\gamma_n L))}} \sinh(\gamma_n x) \xrightarrow{\gamma_n \gg 1} \left(e^{\gamma_n L} + \cos(\gamma_n L) - \sin(\gamma_n L) \right) e^{\gamma_n(x-L)}$$

leading to the following approximated mode shape:

$$\phi_{n_{\text{apx}}}(x) = e^{-\gamma_n x} - \cos(\gamma_n x) + (1 + \nu) \sin(\gamma_n x) - \left(e^{\gamma_n L} + \cos(\gamma_n L) - \sin(\gamma_n L) \right) e^{\gamma_n(x-L)} \quad (6)$$

In particular, for evaluating the finite beam spectrum a set of $N = 200$ modes was adopted, divided as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \phi_n(x) & \text{for } n \in [1, \dots, 20] \\ \phi_{n_{\text{apx}}}(x) & \text{for } n \in (20, \dots, N] \end{cases}$$

Finally, the characteristic equation (3) was solved numerically up to $n = 12$, while for $n > 13$ the following approximated root was considered:

$$\gamma_{n_{\text{apx}}} = \frac{(2n-1)\pi}{2}, \quad (\gamma_{n_{\text{apx}}} - \gamma_n) \Big|_{n>13} = \mathcal{O}(10^{-15})$$

With regard to the infinite beam, a set of $S = 600$ resonators with the same centre spacing parameters of the finite beam have been considered and the following basis of L -periodic complex functions have been used [3]:

$$\phi_{n_{\text{bulk}}}(x) = e^{i\frac{2\pi n}{L}x} \quad \text{for } n \in [-1000, \dots, 1000] \quad (7)$$

The equations related to the finite beam eigenvalues problem are presented below, similar considerations may be drawn evaluating the bulk spectrum.

With reference to equation (2), following the modal decomposition approach it is possible to perform the substitution:

$$w(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x) \eta_n(t)$$

leading to:

$$\begin{cases} EJ \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\partial^4 \phi_n(x)}{\partial x^4} \eta_n(t) + m \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x) \ddot{\eta}_n(t) - k_T \sum_{s=1}^S u_s(t) \delta(x - x_s) = 0 \\ \ddot{u}_s + \omega_T^2 u_s + \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x_s) \ddot{\eta}_n(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Multiplying the first equation by $\phi_k(x)$ and integrating both members over $\int_0^L \dots dx$, considering orthogonality properties of the function basis properly normalized with a factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{mL}}$, it follows that:

$$\begin{cases} \omega_k^2 \eta_k(t) + \ddot{\eta}_k(t) - k_T \sum_{s=1}^S \phi_k(x_s) u_s(t) = 0 \\ \ddot{u}_s + \omega_T^2 u_s + \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x_s) \ddot{\eta}_n(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where ω_k is the angular frequency associated to the k -th mode. Considering an harmonic solution (i.e. substituting $\eta_k(t) = H_{k0} e^{i\omega t}$ and $u_s(t) = U_{s0} e^{i\omega t}$) it is possible to write:

$$\begin{cases} \omega_k^2 H_{k_0} - \omega^2 H_{k_0} - k_T \sum_{s=1}^S \phi_k(x_s) U_{s_0} = 0 \\ -\omega^2 U_{s_0} + \omega_T^2 U_{s_0} - \omega^2 \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x_s) H_{n_0} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Considering now all the $N + S$ equations it is possible to arrange the system in a matrix form as:

$$\begin{cases} -\omega^2 \overbrace{[\mathbb{I}]}^{M_1} \mathbf{H}_0 + \overbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \ddots & & \\ & \omega_k^2 & \\ & & \ddots \end{bmatrix}}^{K_1} \mathbf{H}_0 - k_T \overbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(x_1) & \phi_1(x_2) & \dots & \phi_1(x_S) \\ \vdots & & & \vdots \\ \phi_N(x_1) & \dots & & \phi_N(x_S) \end{bmatrix}}^{Q_1(\theta)} \mathbf{U}_0 = \mathbf{0} \\ -\omega^2 \overbrace{[\mathbb{I}]}^{M_2} \mathbf{U}_0 + \overbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \ddots & & \\ & \omega_T^2 & \\ & & \ddots \end{bmatrix}}^{K_2} \mathbf{U}_0 - \omega^2 \overbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(x_1) & \phi_2(x_1) & \dots & \phi_N(x_1) \\ \vdots & & & \vdots \\ \phi_1(x_S) & \dots & & \phi_N(x_S) \end{bmatrix}}^{Q_2(\theta)=Q_1^T(\theta)} \mathbf{H}_0 = \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

To be noted that the coupling matrix Q_1 (and obviously its transposed Q_2) are the only terms depending on theta. This means that all other matrices could be computed only once, resulting in an improvement of code performances. Considering now the unknown vector $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{H}_0^T \mid \mathbf{U}_0^T]^T$ it is possible to write the problem as:

$$\left(-\omega^2 [M] + [K] \right) \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{0} \quad (12)$$

with:

$$[M] = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} M_1 & \emptyset \\ \hline Q_2 & M_2 \end{array} \right] \quad [K] = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} K_1 & -k_T Q_1 \\ \hline \emptyset & K_2 \end{array} \right]$$

Finally, it is possible to compute the natural frequencies of the system as:

$$\omega = \sqrt{\text{eig}\left([M]^{-1}[K]\right)} \quad (13)$$

At this point, it is sufficient to compute the eigenvalues with different values of $\theta \in [0, 1]$ for both problems and plotting them on the same chart, as shown in Figure 2. Considering the bulk spectrum, it is possible to identify two types of bandgaps at a glance:

- the trivial bandgap, which does not depend on the value of θ and it covers a range of approximately 45 Hz starting from the tuning frequency of the resonators. This is in agreement with what reported by Sugino *et al.* [5], who identifies the bandgap as the frequency region $\omega_T < \omega < \omega_T \sqrt{1 + \mu}$.

Figure 2: Plot of the bulk (black dots) and finite clamped-free beam (red lines) spectra. Vertical lines are related to specific θ values considered in the analysis.

- A set of fractal-like non-trivial bandgaps, recalling the so-called "Hofstadter butterfly". These kind of bandgaps are strongly affected by the parameter θ and thus will be an important subject of this study.

Considering the relationship between bulk spectrum bandgaps and finite beam spectrum, two different cases may arise: if the mode entirely crosses the bandgap it is said to be a topological, while if it simply goes up and down it is called non-topological. Non-topological modes could be further subdivided into trivial and non-trivial ones depending on whether or not they overlap with the trivial bandgap. Another outcome of this preliminary analysis is the determination of relevant values of θ for which conduct the analysis:

- $\theta = 0.175$ ¹. For this value of the QP distribution parameter, the finite beam spectrum crosses some small non-trivial bandgaps.
- $\theta = 0.25$ ¹. The associated clamped-free beam spectrum crosses the middle of an x-shaped non-trivial bandgap at around 215 Hz.
- $\theta = 0.475$. By selecting this particular value of θ , it is possible to investigate the behaviour of the system around the lowest beam natural frequency within the trivial bandgap and through the widest non-trivial bandgaps as well.
- $\theta = 1$. This frontier value was chosen in order to highlight the behaviour of the system far from non-trivial bandgaps.

2. Mechanical system response to base excitation

To compute the Frequency Response Function (FRF) of the cantilever beam with respect to a base excitation it is possible to replicate the approach of the equations (8) and followings. Considering

¹These two values are also adopted by Xia *et al.*[1] in their experimental analysis.

Figure 3: Scheme of a locally resonant metamaterial beam under base excitation [5]. To be noted that in this report the subscript s (instead of j) denotes the specific resonator considered.

the variables of the problem, with reference to Figure 3 the following differences among absolute and relative quantities are pointed out:

$$\begin{cases} w_{\text{abs}}(x, t) = w(x, t) + w_b(t) \\ u_{s_{\text{abs}}} = u_s(t) + w_{\text{abs}}(t) \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Therefore, considering a damping coefficient c_T for all resonators and by implying time dependency of u_s in the resonator equation for sake of clearness, the set of equations describing the system is:

$$\begin{cases} EJ \frac{\partial^4 w(x, t)}{\partial x^4} + m \frac{\partial^2 w(x, t)}{\partial t^2} = k_T \sum_{s=1}^S u_s(t) \delta(x - x_s) + c_T \sum_{s=1}^S \dot{u}_s(t) \delta(x - x_s) - m \ddot{w}_b(t) \\ \ddot{u}_{s_{\text{abs}}} + 2\xi_T \omega_T \dot{u}_s + \omega_T^2 u_s = 0 \quad \xrightarrow{(14)} \quad \ddot{u}_s + 2\xi_T \omega_T \dot{u}_s + \omega_T^2 u_s + \ddot{w}(t)|_{x_s} = -\ddot{w}_b(t) \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

which, after modal decomposition, resembles to:

$$\begin{cases} EJ \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\partial^4 \phi_n(x)}{\partial x^4} \eta_n(t) + m \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x) \ddot{\eta}_n(t) + \dots \\ - k_T \sum_{s=1}^S u_s(t) \delta(x - x_s) - c_T \sum_{s=1}^S \dot{u}_s(t) \delta(x - x_s) = -m \ddot{w}_b \\ \ddot{u}_s + 2\xi_T \omega_T \dot{u}_s + \omega_T^2 u_s + \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x_s) \ddot{\eta}_n(t) = -\ddot{w}_b(t) \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Considering now orthogonality properties of the function basis, introducing a modal damping term and considering an harmonic solution substituting $\eta_k(t) = H_{k_0} e^{i\omega t}$; $u_s(t) = U_{s_0} e^{i\omega t}$; $w_b(t) = W_{b_0} e^{i\omega t}$ it follows that:

simply doing:

$$\mathbf{X} = \underbrace{\left(-\omega^2[M] + i\omega[C] + [K]\right)^{-1} \mathbf{F}\omega^2 W_{b_0}}_{A(\omega)}. \quad (20)$$

Finally, to obtain the FRF of the beam displacement with respect to the real coordinates it is sufficient to multiply the solution vector for the modal matrix:

$$w(x, \omega) = \Phi^T(x)\mathbf{X}(\omega) + 1 \quad (21)$$

The term +1 is needed since for (14) it stands that:

$$w_{\text{abs}}(x, t) = w(x, t) + w_b(t) \quad \longrightarrow \quad \frac{w_{\text{abs}}(x, t)}{w_b(t)} = \frac{w(x, t)}{w_b(t)} + 1 \quad (22)$$

Figure 4: Frequency response function of beam displacement with respect to base motion. "Base" and "Tip" FRF are averaged across [20, 30]% and [90, 100]% of the beam length respectively. Purple lines denotes the values of θ for which a detailed analysis is conducted.

As a preliminary analysis it is possible to consider FRF plots of the beam displacement with respect to base motion shown in Figure 4. With reference to [1], FRF values are averaged across [20, 30]% and [90, 100]% of the beam length (*base* and *tip* FRF respectively) in order to highlight different beam behaviour when approaching the boundaries of the domain. Even if the pattern of the finite beam spectra, shown in Figure 2, underlies both plots, it is possible to highlight as the magnitude of the FRF gets bigger when considering the top FRF. As a result, the trivial bandgap is way smaller and non-trivial bandgaps at higher frequencies nearly disappear.

With reference to Figures 5, 6, 7 and 8 it is possible to draw the following considerations about the behaviour of the systems for $\theta = 0.175$ and $\theta = 0.25$:

- the main difference between the two FRFs, for both values of θ , is located right above the trivial bandgap, since the base one exhibits a second smaller bandgap while the tip one not. This fact is due to the particular QP distribution chosen.

- Considering the beam shape at $f = 131.3525$ Hz for $\theta = 0.175$ it is possible to notice the presence of an edge-localized mode. This fact is reflected by the different amplitude of the FRFs shown in Figure 5 and it is due to the fact that this is a non-topological trivial mode. Same evidences could be found at $f = 151.252$ Hz for $\theta = 0.25$.
- For frequencies equal to the beam spectrum one which are located far for the bandgaps (i.e. $f = 14.2293$ Hz and $f = 230.885$ Hz for $\theta = 0.175$, $f = 27.0373$ Hz and $f = 228.381$ Hz for $\theta = 0.25$) it is possible to point out that any localized mode could be found, as the beam shape exhibits a regular behaviour along its length.

Taking a closer look to the response of the system corresponding to $\theta = 0.475$, shown within Figures 9 and 10, it is possible to point out some differences with respect to the cases examined previously:

- First of all, the non-trivial bandgap immediately above the trivial one is suppressed for both FRFs. This is due to the fact that for $\theta \approx 0.5$ both the beam and the bulk spectrum are rather dense in that frequency range, as depicted by Figure 2. Conversely, a small non-trivial bandgap appears at around $f = 77$ Hz.
- Differently from the aforementioned cases, for $\theta = 0.475$ it is possible to find a certain number of natural frequencies for which the base response is greater than the tip one. Consider, as an example, the beam shapes for $f = 69.1152$ Hz and $f = 235.4848$ Hz shown in Figure 10.
- With regard to the beam shape at $f = 116.9178$ Hz it is possible to highlight the presence of a non-topological trivial tip-localized mode.

Analyzing finally behaviour of the system for $\theta = 1$ (which resembles to a periodic resonators distribution (1)) as shown by Figures 11 and 12 some other considerations could be deduced:

- considering the FRFs of Figure 11 it is possible to notice than any non-trivial bandgap is found. This means that the quasi-periodicity of the resonators' pattern is of primary importance for bandgap opening.
- Considering the beam shape for different frequencies values, corresponding to the trivial bandgap minimum ($f = 90.6511$ Hz) to the first natural frequency after the bandgap ($f = 141.4025$ Hz) and to a condition for which the difference between the two curves is more pronounced ($f = 241.903$ Hz), it is not possible to highlight the presence of any localized beam mode.

2.1. Role of a spatial modulation φ on the localized modes

In order to explore the role of equation (1) in assessing the position of the resonators along the beam, a delay φ has been added, leading to the following modified equation:

$$x_s = sa + R \sin(2\pi \cdot s\theta + \varphi) \quad (23)$$

An effective way to inspect the presence of a certain dependence between the dynamic behaviour of the system and the parameter φ is to generate a plot similar to the one shown within Figure 4, selecting a fixed value of θ and computing the beam displacement FRF for several $\varphi \in [0, 2\pi]$.

As it is possible to notice from Figure 14, the main effect introduced by the phase φ is a shift of the high response frequency bands i.e. the peaks of the FRFs. Clearly, if two consecutive peaks are subjected to a frequency shift of similar magnitude the overall shape of the systems response would not be affected dramatically, while if two subsequent spikes are shifted towards different directions a new non-trivial bandgap may appear. It is possible to find this phenomenon by considering a frequency shift $\varphi \approx \pi\sqrt{3}$ for $\theta = 0.475$, as shown within Figure 14 b), d). It is then also possible to appreciate as for $\pi - 2 \lesssim \varphi \lesssim \pi + 2$ the response of the system at around $f = 200$ Hz is enhanced.

 Figure 5: Averaged FRFs for beam displacement with respect to base motion for $\theta = 0.175$

 Figure 6: Beam shape and resonators configurations at relevant frequencies for $\theta = 0.175$

 Figure 7: Averaged FRFs for beam displacement with respect to base motion for $\theta = 0.25$

 Figure 8: Beam shape and resonators configurations at relevant frequencies for $\theta = 0.25$

 Figure 9: Averaged FRFs for beam displacement with respect to base motion for $\theta = 0.475$

 Figure 10: Beam shape and resonators configurations at relevant frequencies for $\theta = 0.475$

Figure 11: Averaged FRFs for beam displacement with respect to base motion for $\theta = 1$

Figure 12: Beam shape and resonators configurations at relevant frequencies for $\theta = 1$

Figure 13: Schematic of the mechanical locally resonant energy harvesting metastructure. Small cantilever beams with tip masses act as mechanical resonators attached to the primary beam structure, and piezoelectric elements with a resistive load are bonded to the mechanical resonators to serve as energy harvesters [2].

Figure 14: Effect of the phase shift φ on FRFs of beam displacement with respect to base motion for different values of θ . The upper row is related to tip FRFs, while the other one collects base FRFs.

3. Electro-mechanical system response to base excitation

Adding some piezoelectric patches and resistive loads to the strip of steel of each resonator, as shown in Figure 13, it is possible to harvest the mechanical power dissipated by the resonator's motion. Clearly, these changes on structure features will affect also the dynamic quantities considered so far. All relevant data of the electrical counterpart of the system are summarized within Table 2, the only difference with respect to what discussed by Xia *et al.* [1] it's in the thickness of the PZT-5A piezoelectric patches: in order to better highlight the differences among the distinct resistive load tested it was decided to increase it by three times.

To derive the FRF of the relevant quantities of the system depicted it is sufficient to follow the same approach described within Section 2 taking into account both resistors and piezoelectric elements, which act as capacitors. With reference to equation (16), the beam equation remains unchanged, while resonator equation is affected by the piezoelectric element presence and an equation for the electric counterpart appear:

$$\begin{cases} \dots \\ \ddot{u}_s + 2\xi_T \omega_T \dot{u}_s + \omega_T^2 u_s + \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n(x_s) \ddot{r}_n(t) - \Theta_s v_s(t) = -\ddot{w}_b(t) \\ C_{p_s} \dot{v}_s + \frac{1}{R_s} v_s + \Theta_s v_s = 0 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

Where the piezoelectric capacitance C_p and the coupling factor Θ^2 are computed as

$$C_p = \frac{\epsilon_{33}^S}{2h_p} b_s L_s \quad \Theta = e_{31} h_{pc} b_s \left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right|_{L_s} \quad \text{where } h_{pc} = \frac{h_p + h_s}{2}$$

²Being the resonators treated according to a lumped parameters model, only the term $\left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right|_{L_s}$ related to the first mode is considered. This term is kept constant for all resonators [2]

Table 2: Piezoelectric data as described by Xia *et al.* [1]

Feature	Symbol	Unit	Value
Steel strip data			
Length	L_s	mm	82.6
Width	b_s	mm	6.35
Thickness	h_s	mm	0.5
Density	ρ_s	kg/m ³	7850
Elastic modulus	E_s	GPa	200
Piezoelectric patches data			
Thickness	h_p	mm	0.774
Density	ρ_p	kg/m ³	7750
Elastic modulus at constant electric field	C_{11}^E	GPa	61
Piezoelectric constant	e_{31}	C/m ²	-12.3
Electric permittivity at constant strain	ε_{33}^S	$\mu F/m$	13.3

Exploiting modes orthogonality and substituting as done for equation (17) it is possible to arrange all the $N + S + S$ equations in a matrix form as:

$$\begin{cases} \left(-\omega^2 M_1 + i\omega C_1 + K_1 \right) \mathbf{H}_0 + \left(-k_T Q_1 - i\omega c_T Q_1 \right) \mathbf{U}_0 = \omega^2 m \mathbf{F}_1 W_{b_0} \\ \left(-\omega^2 M_2 + i\omega C_2 + K_2 \right) \mathbf{U}_0 - \omega^2 Q_2 \mathbf{H}_0 - Q_3 \mathbf{V}_0 = \omega^2 \mathbf{F}_2 W_{b_0} \\ \left(i\omega C_3 + K_3 \right) \mathbf{V}_0 + Q_3 \mathbf{U}_0 = \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

with $M_1, C_1, K_1, Q_1, M_2, C_2, K_2, Q_2, \mathbf{F}_1, \mathbf{F}_2$ defined as in equation (18) and:

$$C_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \ddots & & & \\ & C_p & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & \ddots \end{bmatrix} \quad K_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \ddots & & & \\ & 1/R & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & \ddots \end{bmatrix} \quad Q_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \ddots & & & \\ & \Theta & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & \ddots \end{bmatrix}$$

Considering now the unknown vector as $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{H}_0^T \mid \mathbf{U}_0^T \mid \mathbf{V}_0^T]^T$ it is possible to write again the problem as:

$$\left(-\omega^2 [M] + i\omega [C] + [K] \right) \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{F} \omega^2 W_{b_0} \quad (26)$$

with:

$$[M] = \begin{bmatrix} M_1 & \emptyset & \emptyset \\ \hline Q_2 & M_2 & \emptyset \\ \hline \emptyset & \emptyset & \emptyset \end{bmatrix} \quad [C] = \begin{bmatrix} C_1 & -c_T Q_1 & \emptyset \\ \hline \emptyset & C_2 & \emptyset \\ \hline \emptyset & Q_3 & C_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad [K] = \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & -k_T Q_1 & \emptyset \\ \hline \emptyset & K_2 & -Q_3 \\ \hline \emptyset & \emptyset & K_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} mF_1 \\ \hline F_2 \\ \hline \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$$

As done within equation (20) it is possible to derive the modal FRF $A(\omega)$ by simply doing:

$$\mathbf{X} = \underbrace{\left(-\omega^2[M] + i\omega[C] + [K]\right)^{-1} \mathbf{F}\omega^2 W_{b_0}}_{A(\omega)}. \quad (27)$$

Once $A(\omega)$ is obtained it is again possible to compute $w(x, \omega)$ in real coordinates as well as the relevant quantities for the analysis of the energy harvesting performances of the system (such as voltage, current and harvested power) which are discussed within section 4.

Considering Figures 15 and 16 and comparing them to the relative chart of the mechanical structure (shown in Figure 9) it is possible to point to point out some effects introduced by the presence of capacitive and resistive elements:

- the main features of the FRF, as the presence of the trivial and non-trivial bandgaps or the frequency regions in which the base FRF is greater than the tip response, are preserved.
- Generally speaking, the addition of a resistive load has the effect of damping the FRF peaks and smoothing the response. Nevertheless, the overall amplitude remains comparable.
- As the resistive load increases, the trivial bandgap moves towards higher frequencies. This is due to the fact that considering an open circuit i.e. $R \rightarrow \infty$ the term Θ^2/C_p act as an extra stiffness term, leading to the so-called *open circuit resonance frequency* [6] $\omega_{oc} = \sqrt{\frac{k+\Theta^2/C_p}{m}}$. The higher is the resistive load the higher will be the actual tuning frequency of the resonators.

Figure 15: Averaged FRFs of beam displacement of the electro-mechanical structure with respect to base motion for $\theta = 0.475$

With reference to Figure 18 it is possible to express the same considerations for a wider range of resistive loads: regardless of whether or not bandgaps are crossed - i.e. $\theta = 0.475$ vs $\theta = 1$ - the main effect brought by the increase of the resistive load is the smoothing of the system's response, highlighted by the slight but gradual blurring of the graph as the resistive load increases. Similar considerations could be drawn by examining Figure 17, in which the differences in the blurring of the two graphs are more pronounced, and the trivial bandgap shift towards higher frequencies is small but fairly evident. To be noted that the underlying finite beam spectra is still present, sign

Figure 16: Effect of the different resistive loads on FRFs of beam displacement with respect to base motion for $\theta = 0.475$

that the addition of a resistive load does not affect the quasi-periodic properties of the metastructure. Considering the beam displacement FRFs at optimal θ shown in Figure 18 it is possible to highlight, in addition to the aforementioned phenomena related to frequency shifting and response smoothing, as the tip response for the higher resistive load appears to be higher within the bandgap and less oscillating right after it. This latter considerations will be punctuated within Section 4, as it could be find observing the plots of the harvested power FRFs at optimal θ shown in Figure 22.

4. Energy harvesting

In order to evaluate the energy harvesting capability of such a structure it is straightforward to consider the FRF of the harvested power, which can be easily derived from equation (27). As one could expect, the optimal resistive load value among all possible one is the result of the competing needs of increasing voltage and current. With reference to Figure 19 it is possible to notice that big differences between base and tip quantities arise: while at the tip the harvested power monotonically increase along the trivial bandgap to decrease right after it gets to the maximum value and before crossing two resonance zones, the base harvested power faces a severe drop at around 200 Hz to become even bigger than the tip one near 235 Hz. All these facts are in agreement with what expressed about Figure 9 and could be equally registered in Figure 15, but in this case the different behaviour is far more evident. It is then possible to notice that the trend of the total harvested power is close to the averaged value on the beam tip, meaning that this region plays a fundamental role with respect to the energy harvesting capability of the whole structure. As regards the effect of the different resistive loads, shown in Figure 20, it is possible to point out the same consideration about response smoothing and target frequency shift discussed within Section 3.

Following the method pursued by Sugino *et al.* [2], Figure 21 shows the resistive load effect on the harvested power as well as the harvested power at optimal load. Comparing the results obtained for $\theta = 0.175$ and $\theta = 0.475$ it is possible to notice that selecting a value of the QP parameter near to the symmetry axis of the spectrum - i.e. $\theta \approx 0.5$ - it possible to improve the power response at optimal load right above the trivial frequency bandgap. Nevertheless, comparing these results with the one obtained for $\theta = 1$, so switching from quasi-periodic to periodic distribution, there are no accentuated differences.

Figure 17: Effect of the QP parameter θ on FRFs of beam tip displacement with respect to base motion. Purple line highlights value of θ for which the output power is maximum at a specific frequency.

Figure 18: a), d) Resistive load effect on FRFs of beam tip displacement with respect to base motion. b), c) FRF of beam tip displacement with respect to base motion at optimal θ for two values of R e), f) FRF of beam base displacement with respect to base motion at optimal θ for two values of R

(a) Power

(b) Current

(c) Voltage

Figure 19: FRFs of electric quantities with respect to beam base acceleration.

(a) Base power

(b) Tip power

(c) Base voltage

(d) Tip voltage

Figure 20: Effect of different resistive load values on FRFs of electric quantities with respect to beam base acceleration.

However, for the purpose of this work, it is more relevant to inspect the effect of a wider range of θ as shown in Figure 22. The first fact that points out is that, as discussed dealing with Figure 17, the different resistive loads does not affect at all the underlying pattern coming from the finite beam spectrum, apart from the aforementioned smoothing effect and trivial bandgap frequency shift. On the other hand it is possible to notice that with the highest load tested the whole response of the system has increased in amplitude. The optimal power lines, in addition, stresses as the maximum power values are found for intermediate values of θ : this means that even if the QP distribution does not radically affect the power FRF, a certain positive correlation between the existence of non-trivial bandgaps and energy harvesting is found. Considering Figure 22 a) - c), in fact, it is possible to appreciate as the optimal θ value is almost always bounded by the non-trivial bandgap tails and that an increase in the resistive load generally helps to reduce the dispersion of the optimal θ around the central value. Finally, Figure 22 d) - f) shows as the maximum load does not always give the best results in terms of absolute maximum harvested power, thus it results in an extremely better power output in the bandgap and, generally speaking, in a more homogeneous frequency response but still far from a broadband application.

Figure 21: a) - c) Resistive load effect on FRFs of total power with respect to beam base acceleration. The grey line represents the optimal load at a specific frequency. d) - f) FRF of total power with respect to beam base acceleration at optimal load.

Figure 22: a) - c) Effect of θ FRFs of total power with respect to beam base acceleration. The grey line represents the optimal value of the QP parameter at a specific frequency. d) - f) FRF of total power with respect to beam base acceleration at optimal θ

5. Conclusions

Through numerical simulations it was possible to reproduce both numerical and experimental results obtained by Xia *et al.* [1] dealing with a cantilever beam carrying an array of 30 resonators. Therefore it has been shown that acting on the parameter defining the quasi-periodic distribution of the locations of the resonators set it is possible to achieve the onset of non-trivial band gaps with associated edge states besides the trivial one, which is still present. Moreover, the effect of a phase shift in the projection operation underlying the quasi-periodic distribution is analyzed, pointing out the possibility to further shaping the system's response peaks as well as its bandgaps.

The response of the system considering the presence of piezoelectric patches and resistive loads connected to each resonator was then analyzed, allowing to identify some distinctive and established features abundantly discussed in the literature. The ability to leverage the presence of localized modes for enhancing energy harvesting performances of such a structure have been finally investigated, highlighting the presence of a certain relation between non-trivial bandgaps and optimal power output.

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